

**A STUDY ON FACTORS AFFECTING UTILIZATION OF FACE MASKS AS A
COVID-19 PREVENTIVE MEASURE, AMONG RESIDENTS OF SOWETO
COMMUNITY UNIT, KAHAWA WARD, ROYSAMBU SUB-COUNTY, NAIROBI
COUNTY, KENYA.**

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this research project is as a result of my study objectives.
Information contained in this research project is my original work and has never been submitted anywhere as an educational requirement in any institution.

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DEFINITION OF TERMS

Mask- This is a face covering designed to filter/block/ restrict fine particulate through them. They usually have ear cords/straps or laces that are used to hold the mask firmly over nose, mouth and chin.

Surgical mask-A face mask is a product that covers the wearer's nose and mouth. Face masks are for use as source control by the general public and health care personnel (HCP) in accordance with CDC recommendations, and are not personal protective equipment.

Covid-19 disease- corona virus disease 2019. A zoonotic respiratory disease that was discovered in the year 2019 in Wuhan china.

Lockdown-A lockdown can be defined as an emergency protocol implemented by the authorities that prevents people from entering or leaving a given area. Either due to health risk or security risk.

Home based isolation and care-This is when a patient confirmed to have COVID-19 is mandated to restrict activities and movements outside their home unless when seeking medical care. Their close contacts are identified and followed up. During the entire period, the patient is followed up by health care worker, the patient should not go to public places the duration is usually 14 days.

Quarantine- this is process of separating and restricts the movement of people who have been exposed to a contagious disease to see if they become sick

Knowledge- facts, information, and skills acquired through experience or education or sensitization

Attitude- A mental and neural state of readiness, organized through experience, exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon the individual's

Standard operating procedures- A standard operating procedure (*SOP*) is a set of step-by-step instructions compiled by an organization to help workers carry out routine operations.

Disinfection- Disinfection describes a process that eliminates many or all pathogenic microorganisms, except bacterial spores, on inanimate objects and surfaces.

Re-use- It means using of the object or material again and again for the same purpose or for different purpose without altering

Health guideline- Guidelines are generally defined as “systematically developed statements to assist practitioners and patients or the general public to make decisions about appropriate health care

Immunity- Immunity refers to the body's ability to prevent the invasion of pathogens. Pathogens are foreign disease-causing substances/organisms, such as bacteria and viruses, and people are exposed to them every day. for specific circumstances to safeguard their health.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

C.H. V	Community Health Volunteer.
COVID-19	Corona Virus Disease 2019
SCDSC	Sub County Disease Surveillance Officer
SCMOH	Sub- County Medical Officer of Health.
SCPHO	Sub- County Public Health Officer
H.C.W	Health Care Worker.
I.C.U	Intensive Care Unit.
H.D.U	High Dependency Unit
MOH	Ministry of Health
GOK	Government of Kenya
N.M.S	Nairobi Metropolitan Services.
K.U.T.R.H	Kenyatta University Teaching and Referral Hospital
S.C.H.P. O	Sub-County Health Promotion Officer
W.H. O	World Health Organization
C.D.C	Centers for Disease Control
N.M. S	Nairobi Metropolitan Service

DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to my beloved parents, Samuel Kiunga and Elizabeth Nyoroka and the entire Thambura family and friends.

ABSTRACT

COVID-19 pandemic first appeared in Wuhan City, Hubei Province of China, in December 2019. With the constant rise in reported cases, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared this outbreak as a global pandemic on the 12 March 2020.¹ This disease which originated from bats and pangolins from Wuhan, China manifests as symptoms of fever, dry cough, and dyspnoea.

On 30th January, 2020 the WHO Director-General declared that the ongoing outbreak of COVID-19 constitutes a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC). The WHO defines a PHEIC as an “extraordinary event” that “constitute[s] a public health risk to other States through the international spread of disease” and “potentially require[s] a coordinated international response.” (IHR 2005).

At the onset of the global pandemic associated with the Coronavirus disease, The Kenyan Ministry of Health (MoH) launched the National Response and Emergency Committee (NERC) to steer the country's prevention, containment, and mitigation measures. Kenya adopted several public health measures to prevent or slow down the transmission of the disease, which the NERC is implementing and promoting.

These include case identification and follow-up of contacts, environmental disinfection, and use of personal protective equipment, social distancing, and regular hand washing with soap or disinfection with hand sanitizer.

Use of face covering was highly promoted and encouraged, since it was a sustainable strategy to cut/combat the spread of covid-19 disease. Kenya Ministry of Health recommends wearing of face masks or cloth face coverings in public settings where other social distancing measures are difficult to maintain (e.g., supermarkets, shops, markets, matatu, buses, boda boda). These masks will prevent the droplets from spreading further and thus protecting others.

To this date masking remains a key measure to stop person to person transmission through contaminated respiratory droplets. Therefore, there is need to study the factors affecting utilization of face masks. This study is aimed at studying the factors that affect utilization of facemasks among the respondents.

The study objectives determined socio demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the Soweto community unit. The study also assessed the level of knowledge, attitude and practices regarding masking as a covid-19 preventive measure among residents of Soweto community unit.

Random sampling was used to select the respondents from the study population. Data collection instrument like structured questionnaires, focused group discussions and in-depth key informant interview schedules and observation checklists were used in the study.

Data from the study was analyzed scientifically and results presented on charts, graphs and tables. The findings of this study assisted in identifying the factors affecting face mask utilization at the community level, potential gaps were identified and recommendations were proposed to address the barriers in order to upscale appropriate use of face masks.

1.0. CHAPTER ONE. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

This chapter describes the background of the study, statement of the problem, broad objective, specific objectives, research questions, study justification and limitations of the study.

1.2. Background Information.

The novel Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) is the major public health burden in the world. The morbidity and mortality of the global community due to this disease is dramatically increasing from time to time. (WHO 2020).

1.3. Broad objectives.

A study on factors affecting utilization of face masks as a covid-19 preventive measure, among residents of Soweto community unit

1.4. Specific objectives.

The study objectives were used to determine socio demographic and socio-economic characteristics of Soweto community unit.

To assess the level of knowledge, attitude and practices regarding masking as a covid-19 preventive measure among residents of Soweto community unit.

1.5. Research questions.

1. What is the socio demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the Soweto community unit?
2. What is the level of knowledge, attitude and practices regarding masking as a covid-19 preventive measure among residents of Soweto community unit?

1.6 Study justification

The Ministry of Health has confirmed a Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) case in Nairobi. The case, which was confirmed on the 12th March 2020, is the first one to be reported in Kenya since the beginning of the outbreak in China in December 2019. From that time there has been increased disease burden of covid-19 disease. Therefore there was need to assess the factors that affect utilization of face masks. Since masking was recommended as the most effective preventive measure by W.H.O and the ministry of health Kenya.

1.7 Null hypothesis.

The null hypothesis for this study stated that, knowledge, attitude and practices do not affect utilization of face masks among sampled residents in Soweto community unit. As a preventive strategy against transmission of covid-19 disease.

1.8 Limitations of the study.

It was hectic to gain access to some households and plots due to the fear of Covid-19 disease. Therefore, the researcher made prior arrangements, to ensure adherence to covid-19 prevention measure during the study was highly observed.

Financial information being a personal description, respondents hesitated sharing their experiences. The challenge was overcome by assuring respondents that the information and data collected was used for the purpose of this study.

Data was handled with confidentiality. Results and responses in a questionnaire contained wrong information from study participants. The limitation was overcome through carrying out a pilot study to minimize wrong responses by participants.

1.9 Assumptions of the study

The researcher assumed that:

- i. The respondents would be available and willing to participate in the research.
- ii. Openness and genuineness of respondents to give accurate answers.

2.0. CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW.

2.1 overview of covid-19 pandemic

Coronaviruses are a large family of viruses that are known to cause illness ranging from the common cold to more severe diseases such as Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS). Human health, animal health and the state of ecosystems are inextricably linked to 70-80% of emerging and re-emerging infectious diseases, which are known to be of zoonotic origin (animal to human transmission), Population growth, and climate change, increasing urbanization and international travel and migration. All these factors increase the risk for emergence and spread of infectious pathogens. Respiratory pathogens, for example In humans they can cause mild disease similar to a common cold – others cause more severe disease (such as MERS and SARS) Some coronaviruses that are found in animals host,

increased interactions has led to these pathogens infecting humans hence zoonotic in nature. (Jebril, 2020,)

Coronaviruses also cause disease in a wide variety of animal species SARS-CoV was transmitted from civet cats to humans in China in 2002 and MERS-CoV from dromedary camels to humans in Saudi Arabia in 2012. Several known coronaviruses are circulating in animals that have not yet infected humans. A spillover event is when a virus that is circulating in an animal species is found to have been transmitted to humans

On 30th January, 2020 the WHO Director-General declared that the ongoing outbreak of COVID-19 constituted a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC). The WHO defines a PHEIC as an “extraordinary event” that “constitutes a public health risk to other States through the international spread of disease” and “potentially requires a coordinated international response.”

2.3 global context

International health authorities suggest that individuals aged 65 years and above and people with underlying comorbidities such as hypertension, chronic lung disease, cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes, and obesity are at increased risk of severe Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19); however, the prevalence of risk factors is unknown in many countries. (Ahrenfeldt et al., 2020)

Three hundred and five thousand, six hundred, (305 641) years of life were lost to COVID-19 in Germany in 2020. The percentage of daily mortality rate by persons under 70 was 34.8% in men and 21.0% in women. 99.3% of the COVID-19 disease burden was accounted for by death. The daily average years of life lost due to death was lower for COVID-19 than for the major non-communicable diseases. Persons who died of COVID-19 lost a mean of 9.6 years of life; those who were under 70 when they died lost a mean of 25.2 years of life. Men lost more years of life than women. (Rommel et al., 2021)

2.4 covid-19 in the African and Kenyan context

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic began in China with a group of severe pneumonia cases, later identified to be caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 in December 2019. Thailand reported the first COVID-19 case outside of China on

13th January 2020, Africa reported its first case in Egypt on 14th February 2020 and Nigeria reported its index case of COVID-19 on 27th February 2020. The Ministry of Health Kenya confirmed a Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) case in Nairobi. The case, which was confirmed on the 12th March 2020, was the first one to be reported in Kenya since the beginning of the outbreak in China in December 2019. ("First case of coronavirus disease confirmed in Kenya," n.d.)

The case was a Kenyan citizen who had travelled back to Nairobi returning from the United States of America via London, United Kingdom on the 5th March 2020. She was confirmed positive by the National Influenza Centre Laboratory at the National Public Health Laboratories of the Ministry of Health. The patient was clinically stable, and was being managed at the Infectious Diseases Unit at the Kenyatta National Hospital. Virtually, all countries in the world are affected, with over 5 million cases reported globally. (Akande & Akande, 2020)

To contain viral spread, several countries continue to use non-pharmaceutical public health interventions,¹⁵⁻¹⁷ including among others border control or closure, partial or complete lockdown, quarantine and testing of incoming travelers and returnees, and mass testing for rapid case detection, contact tracing, and quarantine. Including the most recent intervention, covid-19 vaccination. Masking is still recommended as the effective preventive strategy. After vaccination the clients are sensitized to appropriately mask at all times since everyone is at risk of re-infection. Therefore mask utilization stands a potential topic to research on.

2.4 origin of face masks

In 1897, the hygienist Carl Friedrich Flügge working in Breslau at this time published his works on the development of droplet infection as part of his research on the genesis of tuberculosis , at that time, the respiratory system as a transmitter of germs came into focus of research and already mandated instructions to keep distance. In the same year, 1897, a cooperation work between Flügge and Theodor Billroth's (1829–1894) disciple Johannes von Mikulicz (1850–1905), who also worked in Breslau since 1890, was published. Their publication dealt with performing operations wearing a 'mouth bandage'. In here, Mikulicz described a one-layered mask made of gauze .Mikulicz, who had already been responsible for the introduction of sterile gloves made from cloth, noted concerning the applicability of surgical masks: '*...we breathed through it as easily as a lady wearing a veil in the streets...Medical masks* are defined as surgical or procedure masks

that are flat or pleated. They are affixed to the head with straps that go around the ears or head or both. Their performance characteristics are tested according to a set of standardized test methods that aim to balance high filtration, adequate breathability and optionally, fluid penetration resistance W.H.O (2019)

A face mask is a product that covers the wearer's nose and mouth. Face masks are for use as source control by the general public and health care personnel (HCP) in accordance with CDC recommendations, and are not personal protective equipment.

2.5 socio demographic characteristics.

Demographics is the study of a population based on factors such as age, race, and sex. Demographic data refers to socio-economic information expressed statistically, also including employment, education, income, marriage rates, birth and death rates and more factors. Governments, corporations, and nongovernment organizations use demographics to learn more about a population's characteristics for many purposes, including policy development and economic market research A large and growing body of evidence shows that socio demographic factors – age, race, ethnicity, and language, for example – and socioeconomic status (SES), such as income and education, can influence health outcomes. (America's essential hospital report, 2018). These factors are particularly significant for this study, since they are more likely to influence health outcomes. Different index variables are formed on the basis of socio-demographic variables. They include, for example, socio-economic status, which combines information on education and income. Socio-demographic details are often used as determinants of health and to describe health outcomes in a population and to determine sampling error. Therefore demographic factors were important to be assessed in this study.

2.6 Knowledge, Attitude and Practice factors

The knowledge, attitudes and practices (KAP) toward COVID-19 play an integral role in determining a society's readiness to accept behavioral change measures from health authorities. KAP studies provide baseline information to determine the type of intervention that may be required to change misconceptions about the virus. Assessing the KAP related to COVID-19 among the general public was helpful to provide better insight to address knowledge gaps about

the disease and in the development of preventive strategies and health promotion programs. Schöenberg, et al. (2020).

The knowledge parameters used in this study included, source of information regarding covid-19, knowledge on modes of covid-19 transmission. Knowledge on Preventive strategies, knowledge on proper masking techniques.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, as a key preventive strategy, World Health Organization advised wearing of masks, so as to restrict propulsion and inhalation of respiratory droplets. Attitudes toward wearing masks have not been investigated well. The research aimed to provide data on existing gaps and why people would be willing to wear masks in order to suggest ways for enhancing compliance and sustainability. Attitude factors were assessed, since attitude plays critical role in man behavioral conduct. According to Rieger, M. O. (2020). The factors included, perceived benefits of masking, confidence in masking, respiratory comfort and sharing of masks.

Various practice factors were assessed, to highlight best practices and existing gaps that hinder utilization of face masks. These factors included, masking procedure, masking safety, disposal, use and re-use.

All these factors will give a snapshot of what is affecting utilization of face masks in Soweto community unit.

3.0. CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

3.0 Introduction: background information of the study area.

3.1 County location and size.

Nairobi is the capital city of Kenya. Nairobi is the main commercial center of the country with a well-developed infrastructure, including modern financial and communications systems. Leading domestic and international banks operate from Nairobi. It hosts the country's largest industrial center which accounts for almost 20 percent of the gross domestic product (GDP).

The County's population of 3,138,369 in 2009 is projected to increase to 4,390,158 in 2018. This population is distributed in 17 administrative Sub Counties which have been merged to 10 health Sub Counties for ease of health administration.

Nairobi City County is committed to providing quality and targeted health services that respond to the unique challenges to the population. The county health departments are committed towards addressing the health challenges.

The County government is determined to improve access to quality health services with a special focus on the urban slums through targeted interventions.

3.2 Health profile.

Healthcare in Roysambu Sub County is delivered through public facilities, private facilities and faith-based organizations. It is served by the following health facilities. KUTRH, Kenyatta University Teaching and Referral Hospital, Kahawa West Health Center marurui health center, DCI health center, kamiti prison health center. The area is well covered. There are plans by the Nairobi Metropolitan Service to construct a modern level three hospital at Githurai 44 ward

3.3 Climatic conditions.

The sub-county experiences a temperate tropical climate with two rainy seasons. These rainy seasons used to occur regularly, but due to climate change, the seasons are unpredictable. The annual rainfall ranges between 850mm-1050 mm. with a daily mean temperature of 12-26`C. with January and February being the hottest months.

3.4 Social and Economic activities.

There are multi storied buildings housing numerous small businesses in these areas. The Numerous micro and small businesses in the areas suggests that the informal sector drives the Local economy offering business and employment opportunities. There are also medium and Large businesses like super markets, petrol stations, financial institutions such as banks and Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs), hotels, clubs etc. Public facilities and offices include schools, local administration offices e.g. chiefs, DOs etc.

There are numerous private kindergartens, primary and secondary schools. There is a sub County market in Kahawa West area.

3.5 Administration.

Nairobi County is one of the 47 counties in Kenya and it is the capital city of the republic.

The county has 17 Parliamentary constituencies and the study areas are situated in Roysambu Sub County. The sub county has five wards, namely: kahawa, kahawa west, zimmerman, githurai 44, roysambu.

3.6 Study area.

Roysambu sub-county has an area of approximately 4880 square kilometres, According to the Kenya National Bureau and Statistics, (2019) population and housing census Nairobi County has a population of 4.3 million, Roysambu Subcounty has a population of 433,067.

Roysambu is one of seventeen constituencies in Nairobi County, It was created before the 2013 general election when Kasarani Constituency was split up to form three constituencies: Kasarani, Roysambu and Ruaraka

It borders Mathare sub-county to the south and south-east, Ruaraka and Kasarani constituencies to the east, Ruiru constituency to the north and northeast, Kiambu constituency to the north-west and Westlands constituency to the west.

It contains neighborhoods such as Garden Estate, Thome, Balozi, Zimmerman, Kahawa West and part of Githurai. Kenyatta University, United States International University, National Youth Service headquarters, General Service Unit headquarters, Kamiti Maximum Prison and Kahawa Barracks are also found here.

It has 5 wards namely Roysambu, Zimmerman, Githurai 44, Kahawa and Kahawa West. Kahawa westward has the following community units, Soweto community unit. kiwanja community unit, kongo community unit, kamuthi community unit, kiwanja community unit and Githurai Majengo community unit. The study was carried out in Soweto community unit.

Soweto community unit was established on Saturday 01-10-2011, the C.U has been active. The link facility is Kahawa west health centre. One C.H.V is assigned to the Soweto community unit who works hand in hand with ward C.H.E.W and Community Health Strategy coordinator. The social-economic status of residents of Kahawa-Soweto is low.

3.7 Study design

This study used a cross-sectional study design. This study design was important and useful in finding out factors that affect utilization of face masks among the respondents. The design also

helped to study various factors that include: knowledge related factors, attitude related factors and practices regarding masking utilization as a covid-19 preventive measure.

The study was designed to minimize bias and errors in the entire process, by ensuring pre-testing of data collection tools and use of scientific data handling methods.

This study design was considered appropriate for this study because it is cost effective. The amount of information that was generated was of high quality that can be valid and reliable. Cooper and Schindler (2003) defines the fundamentals of research design as an activity and time based plan, always based on the research question guides, and a framework for specifying the relationship among the study variables and outlined the procedures for every research activity.

The study was designed to observe the necessary ethical requirements throughout the entire process.

3.8 Target population.

A population is defined as a complete set of individuals, cases or objects with some common observable characteristics (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003).

The study was carried out in Soweto community unit in kahawa ward. The respondents comprised all individuals who had attained a minimum age of 18 years or above. Who consented to participate in this study.

3.9 Definition of variables.

- **Independent variables.**

Knowledge

Attitude

Practices

Dependent variables.

Utilization of face masks among the respondents.

3.9.1 Inclusion and execution criteria.

- **Inclusion criteria.**

Respondents in a face mask.

Respondents aged 18 years or above.

Respondents who consented to take part in the study.

- **Exclusion criteria.**

Respondents who did not consent to the study

Respondents below the age of 18 years.

Respondents not in a face mask.

3.9.2 Sample size determination.

Sampling is the procedure whereby a fraction of the data is taken from a large set of data, and the reference drawn from the sample is extended to the whole group (Raj, 1972). According to Kothari (2004) 'a sample design is a definite plan for obtaining a sample from a given population, it refers to a technique or the procedure the researcher would adopt in selecting items for the sample'. Fisher et al formulae will be used.

Fisher et al formulae of 1998 was used to determine the size of the sample: that is Since the target population was estimated to be less than 10000, the required sample size is calculated using the following formula

Where

$$N = Z^2 PQ / D^2$$

Nf = desired sample size (if the population is less than 10000).

N=desired sample size (where the population is more than 10000).

d=degree of accuracy usually 0.5

Z= standard normal deviation which corresponds 95% confidence level or 2

P=population estimated to have a particular characteristics as 0.5

l^2 = Degree of precision; will be taken to be 10%. Since the proportion of the population with the characteristic is not known, then 50%

l=constant

$$Q = (1-P) = 1-0.5=0.5$$

$$Q=0.5$$

Therefore

$$N = \frac{2x^{2(0.5)(0.5)}}{(0.005)^2}$$

$$\frac{4*0.25}{0.0025} = 400 \text{ Constants}$$

Now since the target population is estimated to be less than 10000

$$N = \frac{Z^2 P(1 - P)}{1}$$

$$N = \frac{1.96 \times 0.5(1-0.5)}{(0.1)(0.1)}$$

NF=126 Respondents

Therefore due to logistical factors 100 respondent was interviewed.

3.9.3 Sampling techniques.

Sampling design refers to a research plan that indicates how cases are to be selected for observation or as respondents (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003).

Simple random sampling method was used to select respondents. A simple random sample method takes a small, random portion of the entire population to represent the entire data set, where each member has an equal probability of being chosen.

3.9.4 Data collection

Both primary and secondary data was collected for this study. Primary data was collected using data collection instruments which will comprised of questionnaires and observation checklists. The questionnaires was administered to the respondents who will filled them on their own, with the help and guidance of the researcher.

The following tools were used to collect data; questionnaires, observation checklist, pencil and eraser.

3.9.5 Data analysis.

Data from the study was collected, organized and analyzed scientifically, using statistical software.

The findings were generated, analyzed and recommendations were made from the findings.

3.9.6 Ethical considerations.

Ethical issues are norms a researcher must be aware and consider before starting the research process; to protect the integrity of the researcher and the society/community. Additionally it ensures honest results.

In this study ethical standards were highly upheld by the researcher throughout the process. (Mugenda and Mugenda, (2003). Among the ethical considerations were; integrity, acquiring informed consent from respondents. It was the duty of the researcher to ensure that all those involved are people of integrity and of high moral values who command respect in the society,

The study totally avoided all acts of plagiarism, that is, the act of using other people's ideas and referring to other people's work without acknowledging them.

The researcher obtained a letter of introduction from the University and attached it to the questionnaires before delivering them to the respondents.

The researcher had and displayed valid identities at all time during the study.at all the time

4.0 CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

4.1 Social demographic information

Sex distribution.

Figure 1 sex distribution

Majority 53% of the respondents were female, while 47% were male.

Age.

Figure 2 age distribution

The age distribution across the respondents was as above. Most 38% of the respondents were aged between 18-28 years, 25% aged 30-39 years, 15% age 40-49 years, 12% represented 50-59 years and 10% above 59 years of age.

Level of education.

Level of education	Number of respondents	percentage
Primary	47	47%
Secondary	30	30%
College	13	13%
University	7	7%
none	3	3%

Table 1 level of education

The findings indicated that majority 47% of the respondents had attained a primary level of education. While 3% of the respondents had not attended school.

Religion

Table 2 religion

Majority 77% of the respondents were members of Christian religion, 20% Muslim, 2% Hindu, while 1% represented other religions

marital status

Figure 3 marital status

Majority 72% of the respondents were married, 15% were single, 10% were divorced while 3% were widowed.

Household size

Figure 4 house hold size

Majority 63% of the households had two to four members, while 3% of the households had more than ten members.

Employment status

Figure 5 employment status.

majority, seventy percent of the respondents were self-employed, while thirty percent were employed.

Nature of employment.

Nature of employment	Number of respondents	percentage
government	15	15%
Private sector	10	10%
N.G.O	3	3%
F.B.O	2	2%

Table 3 nature of employment.

Out of the employed population of 70%, majority 15% of the respondents were employed in the government sector. 10% private sector, 3%N.G.O and 2% employed by the faith based organizations.

Monthly Income status

Figure 6 income status.

Majority of the respondents 80% had an estimated monthly income of between 1000-5000 Kenyan shillings. 12% below 1000 Kenyan shillings. While 3% had monthly estimate of above 10,000 Kenyan shillings.

4.2. The level of knowledge.

Covid-19 information.

Figure 7 covid-19 information.

Majority 70% of the respondents relied on mainstream media for health information. 15% relied on internet, 12% health care workers, while 3% of the respondents relied on friends for covid-19 related information.

Covid-19 mode of transmission.

Figure 8 mode of transmission.

Among the sampled population, Majority 74% of the respondents were aware about covid-19 transmission mode. while 5% believed that covid-19 is transmitted through curses.

Covid-19 prevention methods

Figure 9 prevention methods.

From the findings, most 55% of the respondents indicated masking as the best preventive method. Then 25% indicated handwashing, Followed by 17% social distancing and 3% drinking alcohol.

Masking practices

Figure 10 masking practices.

Most of the respondents 30% had knowledge on safe mask practices.

4.3. Attitude towards masking.

preventive benefits.

Perceived benefits	Number of respondents	percentage
Yes	85	85%
no	15	15%

Table 4 preventive benefits.

Majority 85% of the respondents indicated that masking had additional preventive benefits. While 15% indicated otherwise.

perceived benefits.

Figure 11 perceived benefits.

Majority 55% of the respondents indicated that masking protected them from SARS-cov2 virus. Thirty percent indicated protection from dust.

4.4. masking practices.

Masking times.

Figure 12 masking times.

Majority 78% of the respondents had knowledge about the moments of wearing a mask.

Hygienic practices before masking.

majority 55% of the respondents practiced hygiene before handling a face mask, 22% verified the quality

Figure 13 hygienic practices.

of mask, and 20% hold the mask by the straps, .

Mask disposal.

Disposal method	Number of respondents	percentage
Throw away	75	75%
Put in the dustbin	15	15%
burn	10	10%

Table 5 mask disposal.

Seventy five percent of the respondents disposed their used masks by throwing away in the environment. While ten percent burnt their used masks, and 15% disposed in the dustbin for disposal

4.5. Observation checklist

Respondents masking practices.

Figure 14 level of masking.

Majority 76% of the respondents had their masks on. While 24% had no mask

Correct masking.

	Number of respondents	percentage
Yes	56	74%
no	20	26%

Majority 74% of the respondents had properly worn their face masks. While 26% had not worn their masks properly.

Type of mask.

Figure 15 type of mask

Eighty two percent of the respondents had re-usable facemasks, while eighteen percent had single-use/disposable face mask.

Environmental pollution by masks.

Poorly disposed masks in vicinity

Figure 16 mask disposal.

Majority of the environment observed, 77% had a poorly disposed face mask in the vicinity. While 23% had kept their environment tidy.

5.0 CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION.

5.1. Social demographic information

Social demographic variables define the characteristics of the study population. The following social demographic factors were considered and studied in this research study. Age, gender, level of education, employment status, household size and income status.

Gender.

From the findings, Majority 53% of the respondents were female, while 47% were male. This shows sex distribution among the respondents. This data also a component of vital statistics

Age.

The age distribution across the respondents was that, most of the respondents were aged between 18-28 years. This means that the community is majorly composed of youthful population. Who have the potential to sensitize the community on covid-19 disease prevention and help the community to promote their health.

Level of education.

The findings indicated that majority 47% of the respondents had attained a primary level of education. This shows that majority of the respondents have the ability to read and write, this means that they can be able to read and understand key health messages, and also make informed decisions regarding their health.

While 3% of the respondents had not attended school. This means that extra efforts are needed by the health promotion department to reach out to this 3% population in the community.

Religion

Majority 77% of the respondents were members of Christian religion, Muslim, Hindu, while 1% represented other religions. The findings shows that Christianity is the most dominant religion. This is important data that is very useful in planning for health information dissemination. majorly on safe masking practices at soweto community unit.

marital status data indicated/showed that Majority 72% of the respondents were married, 15% were single, 10% were divorced while 3% were widowed.

Household size distribution across the population was that, Majority 63% of the households had two to four members, while 3% of the households had more than ten members.

Employment status indicators showed that majority, seventy percent of the respondents were self-employed, while thirty percent were employed.

Nature of employment.

Out of the employed population of 70%, majority 15% of the respondents were employed in the government sector. while 10% private sector, 3% N.G. O and 2% employed by the faith-based organizations.

Monthly Income status

Majority of the respondents 80% had an estimated monthly income of between 1000-5000 Kenyan shillings. 12% below 1000 Kenyan shillings. While 3% had monthly estimate of above 10,000 Kenyan shillings. This means that some members of the community are not able to afford money to buy facemasks. This brings out a challenge in covid 19 prevention.

5.2. knowledge.

Covid-19 information.

Majority 70% of the respondents relied on mainstream media for health information. 15% relied on internet, 12% health care workers, while 3% of the respondents relied on friends for covid-19 related information.

This data brings out the characteristic of the community being technologically informed. Mainstream media is the fastest, convenient and most trusted source of information. This puts it clear that the health authorities can strengthen the use of mainstream media for health information sharing. Additionally sensitizing and strengthening the health care workforce.

Covid-19 mode of transmission.

From the study, Majority 74% of the respondents were aware about covid-19 transmission mode. This indicates that the efforts by the Ministry of health Kenya to sensitize the communities on covid-19. It is evident that the community is well informed.

while 5% believed that covid-19 is transmitted through curses. This portion of population brings out that there is evident knowledge gap. that needs to be acted on.

Covid-19 prevention methods.

From the findings, most 55% of the respondents indicated masking as the best preventive method. Then 25% indicated handwashing, Followed by 17% social distancing and 3% drinking alcohol.

5.3. attitude and perceptions towards face mask

The data indicates that most of the respondents 25% had knowledge on safe mask practices. And Majority 85% of the respondents indicated that masking had preventive benefits. This means that masking was upheld and practiced as a covid-19 preventive measure in the community.

Among the perceived benefits include, Majority 55% of the respondents indicated that masking protected them from SARS-cov2 virus. Thirty percent indicated protection from dust and many others. It is evident that masking had more benefits apart from protecting the wearer from covid-19.

5.4. masking practices.

Masking times. Majority 78% of the respondents had knowledge about the moments of wearing a mask. Which indicated that safe masking culture was being adopted in the community.

Hygienic practices before masking was also studied, majority 55% of the respondents practiced hand hygiene before handling a face mask. This is a good indicator that contamination is minimized during masking, since the wearer's hands are washed or sanitized by an Isopropyl 70% hand sanitizer.

Mask disposal.

Seventy five percent of the respondents disposed their used masks by throwing in the environment. This practice posed a risk of disease transmission and environmental contamination. While ten percent burnt their used masks as a disposal method.

observation checklist

Majority 76% of the respondents had their masks on. This finding indicated that the community had understood the benefits of masking as a preventive measure against covid-19.

Correct masking was adhered to, Majority 74% of the respondents had properly worn their face masks. From this, eighty two percent of the respondents had re-usable facemasks, while eighteen percent had single-use/disposable face mask. Whis was a good finding.

6.0 CHAPTER SIX: RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS.

6.1. Recommendations

From the research study, the researcher recommended the following.

The researcher recommended the health authorities to conduct more sensitization forums, majorly through the public health department and the health promotion department, to cover the three percent population who do not know how to read and write.

The researcher commended the ministry of health and the entire workforce, for the great work they had done in sensitizing and enforcing adherence to masking. Majority of the community

Figure 17 health education session

The researcher recommended the government of Kenya to involve and engage the youths in the community and strengthen start-ups to scale up employment opportunities, this will raise the income level of households to sustain basic needs for the majority of households without income.

The researcher recommended continued use of mainstream media as fastest, reliable and safe mode of information sharing and community sensitizations. to disseminate health information. Since it is widely used in the community.

The researcher recommended the ministry of health to formulate waste management guidelines for masks at household setting. To control the evident environmental pollution in the community.

The researcher recommended further research about covid 19 disease so that we can have enough data to make informed decision about covid-19 prevention.

The researcher recommends the ministry of health to strengthen public health departments and the health promotion departments to reach more people with key covid-19 preventive measures, majorly masking.

6.2. Conclusions.

The researcher concluded that mask utilization is affected by the following factors: the level of knowledge, attitude and practices in Soweto community unit.

The researcher concluded that the high level of knowledge, attitude and practices on masking was as a result of ministry of health workforce which has scaled-up mask utilization as observed in the study. Therefore, the higher the level of knowledge the higher the utilization face masks.

The researcher concluded that the knowledge gap on mask disposal poses a new challenge associated with mask use.

APPENDICES.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES.

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APPENDIX 2. QUESTIONNAIRE.

A DATA COLLECTION TOOL FOR A RESEARCH STUDY ON FACTORS AFFECTING MASK UTILIZATION, AT SOWETO COMMUNITY UNIT, CONDUCTED BY DAVID MWENDA, STUDENT AT MOUNT KENYA UNIVERSITY.

Directions

- **Your name is not required.**
- **Select your answer by ticking in the box.**
- **Please answer all questions.**
- **The purpose of this study is to fulfill a professional requirement.**
- **Any information provided in this questionnaire is confidential and will be handled with integrity**

Section A: Social Demography

1. What is your age?

- | | |
|--------------------|--------------------------|
| 18 years -29 years | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 30 years -39 years | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 40 years -49 years | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 50 years -59 years | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Above 59 years | <input type="checkbox"/> |

2. What is your gender?

Male female

3. What is your highest level of education?

- | | |
|------------|--------------------------|
| Primary | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Secondary | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| College | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| University | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| None | <input type="checkbox"/> |

4. What is your religion?

Christian Muslim Hindu

Other, specify_____

5. What is your marital status?

Single Married Divorced Widowed

6. What is the size of your house hold?

One member.

2-4 members.

5-7 members.

8-10 members.

Above ten members.

7. Are you employed? Yes No

(b) If yes in 6 (a), what is the nature of employment?

Government

Private sector

Non-governmental organization (NGO)

Others, specify_____

6. What is your average monthly income?

Below 1000

1000- 5000

Above 10000

Section B: knowledge.

1. Where do you get covid-19 information?

- Mainstream media
- Internet
- Health care worker
- Friends

2. How is covid-19 transmitted?

- Respiratory droplets.
- Curse
- Contaminated surface

3. How is covid-19 prevented?

- Masking
- Social distancing
- Drinking alcohol
- Washing hands

4. How do you wear a face mask?

- Cover mouth
- Cover nose
- Cover chin
- All of the above

Section C: attitude.

1. What benefits do you perceive when in a mask?

- Yes
- No

If **yes**, please tick the benefit you perceive.

- Beauty
- Protection from covid-19
- Protected from dust
- All of the above
- Others (Specify) _____

2. How do you feel when in a mask?

- Comfortable
- Uncomfortable

3. Would you share a face mask?

- Yes
- No

Section D. Practices

1. when do you wear a mask?

- when in public areas
- when going to the shop
- when friend visits
- all of the above.

2. What hygiene measures should you perform before wearing a mask?

- Wash hands/sanitize
- Hold the mask by straps
- Check the Integrity of the mask
- All of the above.

3. How do you dispose your mask after use?

- Throw away
- Put in the dust bin
- burn

Section E. observation checklist.

1. Is the respondent in a mask?

Yes no

2. If yes, is it worn correctly?

Yes no

3. What type of mask is the respondent in?

Re-usable mask

Disposable mask

4. Is there a poorly disposed mask at the vicinity?

Yes no

**THANK YOU FOR YOUR TIME,
GOD BLESS YOU.**

APPENDIX 3. BUDGET.

ITEM	UNITS	COST PER UNIT	TOTAL
Transportation for Researcher, Assistant	2	500	1000
Focused group discussion	3	500	1500
In-depth interviews	4	500	2000
proposal development	7	1000	7,000
Stationary			2,000
Research assistants	2	500	1,000
Printing & Binding			2,000
TOTAL			16,500

APPENDIX 4. MAP OF STUDY AREA.

Roysambu Sub County Map

APPENDIX 5. WORKPLAN.

MONTH	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
PROPOSAL DEVELOPMENT					
DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS					
REPORT WRITING					